

Influence of the Interface on Transverse Strength, Creep Behaviour, and Impact Behaviour of Boron and Silicon Carbide Fibre Reinforced Aluminum

G. Jacobsen

Institut für Chem. Technik der Universität Karlsruhe, Kaiserstraße 12, D-7500 Karlsruhe, W. Germany

INTRODUCTION

It is not too difficult to achieve high longitudinal strengthening and stiffening effects in unidirectionally boron and silicon carbide fibre reinforced aluminum. However, not only longitudinal loading conditions appear in practical application of composites, but also off-axis loading. Furthermore, resistance against impact and good creep behaviour are required.

The transverse strength of a unidirectional composite can be improved by a strong interfacial adhesion (1). In contrary, the impact behaviour can only be improved by a controlled weakening of the bonding between fibres and matrix (2). As far as the creep behaviour is concerned, some experimental results have been discussed in literature only in correlations with fibre volume content (3) or fibre spacing (4), but not with the interlaminar shear strength. In any case, the influence of the interfacial adhesion on the mechanical behaviour of composites can be contraversal under different loading conditions.

Al-composites unidirectionally reinforced by boron and silicon carbide fibres were tested in order to study the influence of the interfacial loading conditions. The different grades of interfacial adhesion obtained by varied fabrication conditions and processes (5, these proceedings) were characterized by interlaminar shear strength measurements. The measured data ranged from 30 to 180 MN/m².

EXPERIMENTAL

Composites with comparable fibre volume content, fibre diameter, and fibre spacing were fabricated in laboratory scale with a braze bonding, a diffusion bonding, a foil-filament and a liquid infiltration technique (5, these proceedings). Samples size of 1x4x50 mm was used for flexural tests ($l/d=30$) of transverse strength and for testing of the creep behaviour at 350 °C in flexural arrangement ($l/d=30$). The impact behaviour ($l/d=10$) was tested unnotched accor-

ding to German standard (DIN 53453) with sample size of 4x4x50 mm.

RESULTS

Transverse Strength

The transverse strength data of unidirectionally reinforced composites show within a relatively small scatter a linear relationship with those of the shear strength and do not depend on fabrication process or fibre type (fig. 1). The transverse strength values come to about the double of the shear strength values. This experimental result is in good agreement with theoretical discussions (1).

Fig. 1

Influence of shear strength on transverse flexural strength of unidirectionally boron and silicon carbide fibre reinforced aluminum

It was found that the failure of the samples during transverse strength test (as well as during shear test) occurs only within the matrix if shear strength values exceed 100 MN/m^2 . A typical fracture surface is shown in fig.2a. This behaviour is explained by the strength of the interface which exceeds that of the matrix, and as a consequence the strength of matrix can be utilized completely. The composite transverse strength depends only on matrix strength.

Composites with shear strength values below 100 MN/m^2 show a fracture behaviour with failure within the interface (fig.2b). As a consequence, the transverse strength is limited by the interfacial strength, and the matrix strength can be only incompletely utilized. The interface is too weak and fails before failure would occur in the matrix. An example for extremely poor interfacial bonding is shown in fig. 2c.

Fibre splitting was observed as a third failure mode especially in composites with SiC fibres on carbon substrate and with B_4C -coated boron fibres (fig. 2d).

Impact behaviour

The impact strength of unidirectionally reinforced composites decreases with their shear strength and does not depend on the fabrication processes or fibre type. As shown (fig.3), the relationship is linear if the impact strength is plotted against the reciprocal values of shear strength. This is in accordance with the theoretically developed formalisms (6).

a $BSiC/Al_B: \sigma_{\perp} = 236 \text{ MN/m}^2; \tau = 104 \text{ MN/m}^2$

b $SiC/Al_F: \sigma_{\perp} = 94 \text{ MN/m}^2; \tau = 45 \text{ MN/m}^2$

c $SiC/Al_F: \sigma_{\perp} = 38 \text{ MN/m}^2; \tau = 29 \text{ MN/m}^2$

d $BB_4C/Al_L: \sigma_{\perp} = 154 \text{ MN/m}^2; \tau = 98 \text{ MN/m}^2$

Fig. 2: Fracture surfaces obtained by transverse flexural tests

Fig. 3
Influence of shear strength on impact energy of unidirectionally reinforced boron and silicon carbide fibre reinforced aluminum

The impact behaviour during testing was analyzed by optical record of the speed of falling hammer. Informations on absorbed energy as function of same deflection became thus available.

Fig. 4

Absorbed energy during impact test as function of shear strength of composites

In the small diagram of fig. 4 such a load/deflection curve is schematically shown. The total area below the curve covers the absorbed energy of the tested sample. Three separate ranges can be discussed (7): Range I indicates the elastic deformation of fibres and matrix, range II the plastic deformation of the matrix, further elastic deformation of the fibres until crack starts, and parts of that energy which is adsorbed by debonding of the fibre matrix interface. Range II is deduced from the fibre pull out and further deformation of the matrix ending with total failure.

Fig. 5: Fracture surfaces obtained from impact tests
 a) BSiC/Al_F (600°C fabrication temperature)
 $a_n = 75 \text{ kJ/m}^2$; $\tau = 97 \text{ MN/m}^2$
 b) $\text{BB}_4\text{C}/\text{Al}_F$ (500°C fabrication temperature)
 $a_n = 180 \text{ kJ/m}^2$; $\tau = 47 \text{ MN/m}^2$

In the main part of fig. 4 these three separated parts of adsorbed energy are plotted against the shear strength of the composite. As theoretically expected, range I (only elastic deformation) increases with increased shear strength but only at the low level up to 25 MN/m^2 . Ranges II and III decrease rapidly with increasing shear strength of the composite. The absorbed energy in range III is larger than in range II, but falls to zero at shear strength values between 95 and 110 MN/m^2 . This behaviour can be

explained by the absence of any fibre pull out. Fig. 5a shows the fracture surface of such a typical brittle fracture. Composites with lower shear strength show a considerable amount of fibre pull out (fig. 5b) with fibre-pull out length exceeding some fibre diameters.

Creep behaviour at elevated temperatures (350 °C)

The creep behaviour was tested at a constant temperature of 350 °C. This temperature can be considered as upper limit for long time application of B/Al composites (8,9).

400 MN/m² and 500 and 600 MN/m² were applied as load during testing. The creep rate is defined as the deflection of the samples (in %) per time (per 100 h) during the second creep stage (steady creep state).

Fig. 6

Creep curves of unidirectionally uncoated boron fibre reinforced aluminum

Typical creep curves are shown in fig. 6. The B/Al samples differ because of their varied fabrication temperatures. Creep rate and total deflection are minimum if maximum fabrication temperatures were applied (equivalent to interfacial adhesion). Also the deflection ϵ_0 in the beginning of tests is influenced in the same direction. The (reverse) deflection ϵ_E after deloading, normalized by the loading deflection ϵ_0 is increased with increasing fabrication temperature from 0.5 (475 °C) to 0.9 (600 °C). Also this behaviour indicates that adhesion is improved by increasing the fabrication temperature.

The creep test results of all composites unidirectionally reinforced with 140 μ m fibres are compiled for three different loads in fig. 7. The creep rate decreases with increasing shear strength of the composite. A linear relationship is found if creep rates are plotted against reciprocal shear strength. Heavier loads cause increased creep rate, but different fabrication procedures or fibre types do not influence the creep rate.

As far as the influence of interfacial adhesion on creep behaviour is concerned, it was found to be unimportant whether shear test failure occurs within the interface or the matrix. This finding is valid only for composites with a shear strength above 100 MN/m². In case the shear strength does not exceed 100 MN/m² one can conclude from the results that the creep of the composites is mainly

Fig. 7

Influence of shear strength on creep rate of unidirectionally boron and silicon carbide reinforced aluminum

controlled by the interface. The improved creep behaviour of the composites showing higher shear strength values is effected by matrix strengthening.

Fig. 8

Influence of fibre diameter on creep curves of unidirectionally boron fibre reinforced aluminum

Also the influence of the fibre diameter on the creep behaviour was investigated. For these tests uncoated boron fibres with 100, 140 and 200 μm diameter were used. The creep curves of fig. 8 show that larger fibre diameters and therewith larger matrix bridges in loading direction increase the total deflection and creep rate. Especially the dimension of the matrix bridges seems to dominate the creep behaviour. This can be recognized by comparison of the creep data of composites containing 140 μm fibres either with a fibre spacing of 0.20 mm (fig.8) or of 0.15 mm (fig.6, 500 °C sample).

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results (fig. 9) confirm that the transverse strength of unidirectionally reinforced aluminum composites is improved by a strong interfacial adhesion. Under the precondition of sufficient adhesion the transversal strength is dominated by strength of the aluminum matrix. As far as the creep behaviour is concerned, inverse correlation of creep rate with the interlaminar shear

Fig. 9

Influence of shear strength on impact energy, creep rate and transverse strength of unidirectional boron and silicon carbide fibre reinforced aluminum

strength was found. Samples with highest values of shear strength show lowest creep rates. However, the impact strength can be only improved by a controlled weakening of the interfacial adhesion. Analysis of the impact behaviour show that high impact energy can be contributed to the energy consuming which is caused by debonding of the fibre/matrix interface and mainly by fibre pull out.

This contraversal influence of the interfacial adhesion on the mechanical properties of fibre reinforced composites can become disadvantageous in practical application. In turbine blades for instance good impact behaviour is required combined with good creep resistance and high transversal strength.

Aluminum composites especially if reinforced by coated boron fibres can be considered as excellent material in practical application where impact behaviour is not important. In such cases the matrix strength can be utilized completely, and a good creep resistance can be expected. If the alloy AA 6061 is used as matrix material transverse flexural strength of the composites up to 300 MN/m² and creep rates less than 0.3 % per 100 h (at 350 °C and 400 MN/m² load) can be expected in composites with a shear strength of 130 MN/m². Composites showing such interfacial adhesion can be fabricated without decisive loss of longitudinal strengthening effect (5, these proceedings). Further improvements to higher shear strength values and therewith to better transversal strength and a better creep behaviour are achievable, however, combined with a decrease of longitudinal strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author thanks Dr. H. LEIS, Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm, München, and Mr. R. KOCHENDÖRFER, DFVLR, Stuttgart, for experimental support. The work was financed by the German Department of Defence.

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